

Review

Complement resistance mechanisms of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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ABSTRACT

The current emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria causes major problems in hospitals worldwide. To survive within the host, bacterial pathogens exploit several escape mechanisms to prevent detection and killing by the immune system. As a major player in immune defense, the complement system recognizes and destroys bacteria via different effector mechanisms. The complement system can label bacteria for phagocytosis or directly kill Gram-negative bacteria via insertion of a pore-forming complex in the bacterial membrane. The multi-drug resistant pathogen *Klebsiella pneumoniae* exploits several mechanisms to resist complement. In this review, we present an overview of strategies used by *K. pneumoniae* to prevent recognition and killing by the complement system. Understanding these complement evasion strategies is crucial for the development of innovative strategies to combat *K. pneumoniae*.

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1. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

K. pneumoniae is a non-motile Gram-negative aerobic rod that causes a wide variety of hospital-acquired infections. This bacterium colonizes a wide range of hosts ranging from plants to mammals, but can also be found in the soil and surface water (Podschun et al., 2001). Normally, individuals carry *K. pneumoniae* asymptomatically on the skin, in the nose and throat (Bagley, 1985). In immunocompromised individuals, neonates and the elderly, *K. pneumoniae* can cause severe hospital-acquired infections such as pneumonia and urinary tract infections. In addition, certain hyper-

virulent *K. pneumoniae* strains can cause community-acquired infections (Brisse et al., 2009). Acquisition of antibiotic resistance genes and intrinsic resistance to several classes of antibiotics limits treatment options for infections caused by *K. pneumoniae*. Currently, *K. pneumoniae* strains producing Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamases (ESBLs) and carbapenemases have spread globally (Hawkey and Jones, 2009). These enzymes inactivate β -lactams, a class of antibiotics that forms the basis of effective treatment for patients suffering from infections with *K. pneumoniae*. As a result the antimicrobial peptide (AMP) colistin (also known as polymyxin E) has been reintroduced to treat infection with multidrug resistant *K. pneumoniae*. However, the acquisition of colistin resistance by chromosomal mutations and the plasmid-associated gene *mcr-1* have recently been reported (Liu et al., 2015; Olaitan et al., 2014), acutely threatening the effectiveness of colistin as an antibiotic of

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last resort for multi-drug resistant *Klebsiella* infections. Some clinical *K. pneumoniae* isolates are resistant to all available antibiotics (Elemam et al., 2009). The rise of these multi-drug resistant isolates warrants the development of novel classes of antibiotics or alternative treatment strategies.

Traditionally, classification of *K. pneumoniae* isolates was performed by capsular serotyping (K-typing) using specific antisera (Podschun and Ullmann, 1998). There are 79 capsular serotypes, but the majority of infections in humans are caused by a limited number of serotypes (Brisse et al., 2013). *K. pneumoniae* strains belonging to the K1 and K2 serotypes are known as hypervirulent, causing community-acquired infections in the form of pyogenic liver abscesses (Fung et al., 2002; Struve et al., 2015). Next to capsular typing, *K. pneumoniae* isolates are also typed on the basis of the polysaccharide O-antigen (O-typing). The O-antigen protrudes from the outer membrane and is the outermost domain of lipopolysaccharide (LPS) that form an essential component of the cell wall of Gram-negative bacteria. The O1 serotype is the most prevalent serotype among clinical isolates (Hansen et al., 1999). Recently, differentiation by genome sequencing has been introduced (Bialek-Davenet et al., 2014). Detailed genomic analysis revealed that strains belonging to clonal complex 258 (CC258) are highly enriched in *K. pneumoniae* isolates originating from hospital-acquired infections (Holt et al., 2015).

To survive within the human host, bacteria have developed several lines of counter-attack and evasion strategies. Like many other opportunistic pathogens, *K. pneumoniae* has various virulence factors that help the bacterium survive within the host (Podschun and Ullmann, 1998). However, compared to other clinically important bacteria, the repertoire of genes involved in colonization and infection is incompletely defined. As one of the most obvious protective structures the capsule has been well-studied in *K. pneumoniae* (March et al., 2013). The capsule protects against phagocytosis, antimicrobial peptides and complement-mediated lysis. Hypervirulent *K. pneumoniae* strains, belonging to clonal complex 23 acquired a large virulence plasmid encoding different virulence factors, including siderophores (Struve et al., 2015). The acquisition of iron via siderophores is crucial for growth and virulence within the host. Deletion of the gene encoding for the siderophore aerobactin reduced growth in serum and virulence in a lung infection model (Russo et al., 2015). In order to colonize the host, *K. pneumoniae* uses type I pili for adherence to different surfaces like the mucosa (Murphy et al., 2013; Rosen et al., 2015). Deletions of genes involved in type I pili synthesis and regulation reduce virulence in mice. After colonization, *K. pneumoniae* can survive, for instance in alveolar macrophages, to evade killing in the phagosome (Cano et al., 2015).

Because of its emergence as a multi-drug resistant pathogen, it is crucial to better understand the mechanisms by which *K. pneumoniae* can survive within the human host. Apart from virulence mechanisms to adhere to tissues (pili) or acquire iron (siderophores), this bacterium has also evolved ways to circumvent clearance by the immune system, which is an important requisite for pathogenic bacteria. Although our collective insights into complement evasion mechanisms of *K. pneumoniae* have increased, these have not yet been subject for review. Here, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the interactions of this important human pathogen with the complement system.

2. The complement system

The complement system belongs to the first line of immune defense and consists of a network of plasma proteins that trigger a proteolytic cascade upon recognition of several microbial patterns (Ricklin et al., 2010; Walport, 2001). Activation leads to

the deposition of complement proteins on the bacterial surface, thereby labeling bacteria for phagocytic uptake and subsequent killing. Three distinct pathways initiate complement activation. In the classical complement pathway, the complement protein C1q recognizes antigen-antibody complexes and triggers the generation of C3 convertase enzymes, which cleave the complement protein C3 into C3b, which covalently attaches to bacterial surfaces (Fig. 1a). Similarly, in the lectin pathway Mannose-Binding Lectin (MBL) or ficolins that recognize sugar motifs or cell wall polymers that are specifically present on microbial surfaces trigger the formation of a C3 convertase. The alternative pathway is generally seen as an amplification loop to enhance C3b deposition following initiation of complement activity via the classical and lectin pathway.

Complement receptors expressed on phagocytic cells recognize C3b on bacteria, triggering phagocytosis of the opsonized bacteria. After phagocytosis, bacteria end up in the phagosome where they are attacked by several antimicrobial proteins and reactive oxygen species. The deposition of C3b also triggers formation of C5 convertases that cleave C5 into C5b, which initiates the formation of the membrane attack complex (MAC). This multi-protein complex consists of the proteins C5b, C6, C7, C8, and multiple copies of C9 (C5b-9) and can specifically kill Gram-negative, but not Gram-positive bacteria, via pore formation in the outer membrane (Berends et al., 2014). The cell wall of Gram-negative bacteria consists of an outer membrane, a periplasmic space with a thin peptidoglycan layer, both of which lie outside the inner membrane (Fig. 1b). The MAC targets the outer membrane, however the exact mechanism by which the MAC causes cell lysis in Gram-negative bacteria remains unclear (Berends et al., 2014). In Gram-positive bacteria, the thick peptidoglycan layer is thought to prevent lysis by the MAC. Next to stimulating phagocytosis and direct killing through MAC-mediated bacterial cell lysis, the chemoattractant C5a is also released during the proteolytic cascade of the complement system and attracts immune cells to the site of infection. Furthermore, the adaptive immune response can be enhanced as a result of complement activation. This can be achieved in various ways, for instance by inducing cross-talk between antigen presenting cells or via detection of complement cleavage products by complement receptors expressed on B and T cells (Carroll and Iseman, 2012; Strainic et al., 2008; Wagner et al., 2006).

3. Complement activation by *K. pneumoniae*

Before we discuss complement evasion, we will first describe how the complement cascade is activated on *K. pneumoniae*. First, outer membrane proteins and lipopolysaccharide of *K. pneumoniae* are known to activate the classical pathway (Alberti et al., 1996a). Binding of C1q activates C1s resulting in formation of a C3 convertase that cleaves C3 into C3b, exposing a previously hidden thioester that covalently links C3b to surfaces in close proximity to the activation site. As surface exposed molecules, lipopolysaccharide and outer membrane proteins (OMPs) in *K. pneumoniae* serve as important targets for C3b deposition (Alberti et al., 1996a; Galdiero et al., 1984; Mishra et al., 2015). OMPs have various roles in the interaction with the immune system of the host, such as resistance against antimicrobial peptides and activation of dendritic cells (Jeannin et al., 2000; Llobet et al., 2009). The abundantly expressed outer membrane protein K36 (OmpK36) of *K. pneumoniae* binds C1q in an antibody-independent way and activates the classical pathway (Alberti et al., 1993, 1996b). The globular domains of the heterotrimer C1q directly interact with OmpK36 of *K. pneumoniae* (Alberti et al., 1996b; Kojouharova et al., 2003). This direct interaction also leads to complement activation, resulting in the deposition of C3b and C5b-9. Furthermore, purified LPS from

Fig. 1. Complement activation and the Gram-negative cell structure.

(A) Schematic overview of the complement system. Activation occurs via recognition of antibodies by C1q in the classical pathway or via recognition of sugar motifs via MBL or ficolins. This leads to activation and cleavage of several complement proteins leading to deposition of C3 convertases that cleave C3 into C3b. The alternative pathway amplifies C3 cleavage by generating additional C3 convertases leading to massive C3b labeling of the bacterial surface. The deposition of C3b triggers phagocytosis and formation of C5 convertases that cleave C5 into the chemoattractant C5a and C5b, which initiates formation of the membrane attack complex. (B) Gram-negative bacteria have a thin peptidoglycan layer located in the periplasmic space between the outer and inner membrane. The capsule consists of a polysaccharide layer that protects the bacterium from the outside environment.

K. pneumoniae can activate the alternative complement pathway (Alberti et al., 1993). The structure of LPS differs between *K. pneumoniae* strains and influences the potency to activate complement, as will be discussed later.

Capsular polysaccharide patterns of some *K. pneumoniae* strains can induce activation of the lectin complement pathway via the interaction with MBL (Sahly et al., 2009). This occurs by recognition of capsular polysaccharides containing mannobiose or rhamnose. Poorly encapsulated strains show a relatively high level C3b on their surface and are phagocytosed by lung epithelial cells (Astorza et al., 2004; Cortés et al., 2002a). Loss of the capsular polysaccharides inhibits virulence, which correlates with loss of serum resistance as will be discussed in more detail in the next sections.

4. Complement evasion strategies by *K. pneumoniae*

4.1. Protection by the capsule

The capsule of *K. pneumoniae* is a dense, ~160 nm thick layer of polysaccharide fibers that effectively protects the bacterium from hostile environments (Amako et al., 1988). Deletion of the

genes necessary for capsule formation in clinical strains drastically impairs virulence of *K. pneumoniae*, resulting in a virtually non-pathogenic bacterium (Lawlor et al., 2005). Capsular polysaccharides are high molecular weight structures with linear or branched repeating units of two to seven monosaccharides (Zamze et al., 2002). Capsular switching of *K. pneumoniae* strains belonging to the hospital-enriched CC258 indicates that the composition of the capsular polysaccharide can quickly change and is important for virulence (Wyres et al., 2015). Several studies showed that the capsule of *K. pneumoniae* provides an efficient barrier to prevent bacterial killing via the MAC (Fig. 2a) (Clements et al., 2007; Fang et al., 2004; Lin et al., 2012). In clinical isolates the capsule protected against serum killing and C3b deposition via the three different complement activation pathways (Alvarez et al., 2000; Merino et al., 1992). The deposition of C3b is dependent on the thickness of the capsule of *K. pneumoniae*, probably because the capsule masks antibody epitopes on the bacterial surface, potentially blocking the activation of complement entirely (Astorza et al., 2004; Domenico et al., 1999).

The capsular polysaccharide motifs vary between different *K. pneumoniae* strains and are detected to different degrees by the innate immune system. Certain *K. pneumoniae* strains can mod-

Fig. 2. Complement evasion by *K. pneumoniae*.

(A) Role of the capsule in complement evasion. *K. pneumoniae* modifies sugar structures that fail to activate the lectin pathway, thereby preventing C3b and MAC deposition. In addition, the thick polysaccharide layer creates a physical barrier around the bacterium that prevents proper insertion of the MAC and subsequent bacterial lysis. RfaH and HtrA increase serum resistance and have been associated with a change in capsule formation. (B) Evasion of complement activation by LPS. Elongation of the O-antigen blocks recognition of surface epitopes by antibodies or directly via C1q and activates complement far from the outer membrane, which prevents proper insertion of the MAC into the outer membrane. In addition, O-antigen side chains decrease deposition of C3b and the MAC. Modified glycan structures at the terminal end of the *K. pneumoniae* O-antigen diminish complement activation.

ify their capsular composition to prevent recognition by the lectin pathway, as was reported in strains of the K2 serotypes that have an altered glycan composition (Sahly et al., 2009). These strains lack mannobiose or rhamnobiase, which are recognized via the lectin pathway. Sialylation of the terminal end of capsular polysaccharide slightly inhibits complement-mediated phagocytosis of hypermucoid *K. pneumoniae* strains (Lee et al., 2014). The enzymatic removal of sialic acid restored complement-mediated phagocytosis. In conclusion, the capsule of *K. pneumoniae* forms an important shield that limits complement activation, in addition to other important functions such as protection against antimicrobial peptides.

4.2. Lipopolysaccharide

The capsule forms the major physical barrier for the membrane attack complex, but the outer membrane of *K. pneumoniae* forms the main target for the MAC. As a major component of the Gram-negative cell wall, lipopolysaccharide (LPS) plays an important role in outer membrane stability and protection against the outside environment. For Gram-negative bacteria, LPS is crucial for fitness, but modifications in LPS are common and necessary to adapt to different environments (Needham and Trent, 2013). LPS consists of a glycan polymer or O-antigen that is connected with a polysaccharide core to lipid A, which is hydrophobic and anchors LPS into the bacterial outer membrane (Fig. 1b). Cationic antimicrobial peptides can disrupt the outer membrane by displacing cations such as Mg^{2+} which normally stabilize the outer membrane through electrostatic interactions between lipid A moieties. Moreover, the innate immune system recognizes the lipid A part of LPS via Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4), which is expressed on various immune cells and reacts upon the detection of LPS with cellular activation and cytokine production (Poltorak et al., 1998). Variations in the structure of lipid A drastically affect the capacity of lipid A to stimulate TLR4. Additionally, lipid A modifications may possibly influence the interaction with the host complement negative regulator factor H, as previously observed for *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (Lewis et al., 2010). *K. pneumoniae* has also evolved several mechanisms by which it can modify its lipid A during colonization and infection, indicating that lipid A modifications are essential to ensure survival within the host (Lobet et al., 2015).

In several Gram-negative bacteria, other modifications of LPS have been shown to lead to changes in serum resistance (Schiller and Joiner, 1986). Such LPS modifications include elongation and changes in polysaccharide composition of the O-antigen side chain. The O-antigen is highly variable and is recognized by antibodies since this part of LPS is surface exposed. *K. pneumoniae* strains with a long O-antigen produce a high molecular weight (smooth phenotype) LPS, whereas strains lacking O-antigen side chains have a low molecular weight (rough phenotype) LPS. In general, strains with rough LPS are more susceptible to serum killing, compared to strains with smooth LPS (Ciurana and Tomas, 1987; McCallum et al., 1989). Interestingly, isolates with rough LPS activate the classical pathway, whereas smooth LPS activates the alternative pathway (Alberti et al., 1993). The long O-antigen in smooth LPS probably protects either direct C1q binding or binding to antibodies directed against *K. pneumoniae* surface molecules. Consequently, elongation of the O-antigen side chains leads to C3b deposition further away from the surface (Merino et al., 1992). This prevents proper deposition of the MAC on the bacterial membrane, resulting in reduced pore formation and bacterial killing. Analysis of opsonization of different *K. pneumoniae* strains revealed slightly lower C3b and no C5b9 deposition on the bacterial surface of serum resistant strains (Merino et al., 1992). This illustrates that *K. pneumoniae* can block the formation of the MAC by two mechanisms, either by sterically hindering the MAC from reaching the outer membrane or by inhibiting complement deposition by blocking epitopes of surface molecules recognized by antibodies or by C1q directly (Fig. 2b). In other Gram-negative bacteria elongation of the O-antigen prevents killing by the MAC in a similar way (Grossman et al., 1987; Kintz et al., 2008; Phan et al., 2013). Adding purified *K. pneumoniae* LPS to strains that are sensitive to serum effectively inhibited serum-mediated killing, in contrast to purified capsular polysaccharides (Merino et al., 1992). Finally, *K. pneumoniae* and other Gram-negative bacteria secrete LPS-containing outer membrane vesicles that can absorb complement proteins, thereby inhibiting complement deposition on the bacterial surface (Lee et al., 2012; Pettit and Judd, 1992).

An epidemic multi-drug resistant *K. pneumoniae* clone (CC258) causes problematic hospital-acquired infections, which are difficult to treat due to widespread antibiotic resistance (Tzouveleakis et al., 2013). Isolates belonging to this clone have a modified capsule and the majority of the strains in CC258 also have a modified O-antigen structure (Szijártó et al., 2015; Wyres et al., 2015). O-antigens consists of galactose repeats (i.e. galactan) that varies depending on the O-antigen serotype (D-galactan I or II). These galactans have a different capping of the galactose repeat resulting in a change of antigenicity. Recently, a modified D-galactan I structure was identified in ST258 and named D-galactan III (Szijártó et al., 2015). Strains of ST258 expressing D-galactan III show an improved survival in human serum compared to isogenic strains expressing D-galactan I. In contrast, another study showed no effect on serum-mediated bacterial killing when deleting the gene encoding a galactosyltransferase responsible for synthesis of the D-galactan I of the O-antigen (Shankar-Sinha et al., 2004). These findings suggest that the O-antigen composition is not directly involved in serum resistance. However, in the same study the authors also show that the O-antigen contributes to virulence in a complement C3-dependent way, suggesting that *in vivo* other complement effector functions play a more important role than lysis by the MAC. The use of different *K. pneumoniae* strains may explain variations between studies regarding the role of the O-antigen in serum resistance. In summary, the O-antigen plays a major role in modulation of complement activation in *K. pneumoniae*.

4.3. Outer membrane proteins

In addition to the modification of the capsular polysaccharides and LPS structures, *K. pneumoniae* also uses outer membrane proteins to escape detection by the complement system. Deletion of the genes encoding the outer membrane proteins peptidoglycan-associated lipoprotein (Pal) and murein lipoprotein (LppA) reduced serum survival of *K. pneumoniae*, in contrast to deletion of *ompA* (Hsieh et al., 2013). Deletion of *lppA* decreased the ability of *K. pneumoniae* to survive in serum only slightly, whereas serum susceptibility increased dramatically in the *pal* deletion mutant. In addition to increased serum susceptibility, phagocytosis of the *pal* and *lppA* mutants was increased considerably (Hsieh et al., 2013). The exact role of Pal and LppA in resistance of *K. pneumoniae* against phagocytosis, and whether reduced complement activation is responsible for impaired phagocytosis, remains to be determined. A similar screening in uropathogenic *E. coli* also identified murein lipoprotein as an important protein for serum survival (Phan et al., 2013). Both the *pal* and *lppA* mutants have an increased outer membrane permeability, which probably contributes to the increased susceptibility to serum. Furthermore, loss of the outer membrane protein OmpK36 contributes to enhanced antibiotic resistance and is regularly observed in antibiotic resistant isolates (Xuan et al., 2009). Deletion of the gene encoding the outer membrane protein OmpK36 increases serum resistance slightly (Chen et al., 2010), but, in contrast, also increases the uptake by neutrophils and the mutant is therefore less virulent in an animal model. The loss of a direct interaction between OmpK36 and C1q may explain enhanced serum resistance in the *ompK36* deletion mutant, although the increase in phagocytosis indicates that complement is still functional in the absence of OmpK36. These observations suggest that antibiotic resistance and resistance to complement are delicately balanced and may make it difficult to predict to what extent these mechanisms contribute to the success of *K. pneumoniae* as a nosocomial pathogen.

4.4. Other complement resistance strategies

As indicated above, complement evasion by *K. pneumoniae* is mainly established by modifying the capsule, LPS or outer membrane proteins. This strategy seemingly contrasts with the mechanisms used by Gram-positive bacteria, which produce several secreted proteins that directly inhibit or degrade complement proteins (Laarman et al., 2010). Furthermore, several pathogens express surface-associated molecules to attract host regulators of complement. For instance, many bacteria express surface proteins that recruit human factor H to their surface to inactivate surface-bound C3b (Ferreira et al., 2010). For *K. pneumoniae* recruitment of factor H or direct interaction with factor H has not yet been described, but it has been suggested that sialic acid residues in the *K. pneumoniae* capsule may have this function or, alternatively, that certain lipid A modifications may have this role (Lee et al., 2014; Lewis et al., 2010).

Screening methods using transposon mutagenesis have identified genes which are important for survival in serum or during infection (Bachman et al., 2015). By analyzing a transposon mutant library in a murine lung infection model several genes that are important for survival of *K. pneumoniae* have been identified. Among these genes was *rfaH*, a gene encoding a transcriptional elongation factor. A *rfaH* deletion mutant showed increased serum susceptibility and reduced fitness in a murine lung infection model. RfaH promotes the transcription of several virulence genes including capsule and LPS synthesis genes, confirming other studies that showed that these structures are important for complement resistance. Homologs of RfaH can be found in other pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae, where they also contribute to virulence (Kong et al., 2011; Nagy et al., 2002). Another *K. pneumoniae* gene, *aroE*, which is involved in the synthesis of aromatic amino acids also showed an increased susceptibility to serum, combined with a decrease in mucoviscosity. The mechanism of serum resistance of this mutant remains unclear.

Another transposon mutant library screen to identify mutants that are serum susceptible identified the *htrA* gene as being important for serum survival (Cortés et al., 2002b). The *htrA* gene encodes a serine protease that affects capsule formation. A *htrA* deletion mutant showed increased opsonization with C3b and susceptibility to serum killing. Notably, no *K. pneumoniae* proteins that directly interact and evade killing by the complement system were identified in transposon screens. Transposon mutant library screenings with strains from different genetic backgrounds may help to identify novel complement evasion proteins, especially since *K. pneumoniae* has a large accessory genome with over 30,000 protein coding genes (Holt et al., 2015).

5. Directions for future research

Most studies on the interactions of *K. pneumoniae* with serum primarily determine the extent by which strains are sensitive to serum, but they do not determine whether the bactericidal effect of serum is mediated by the complement system. Other antimicrobial agents in serum, including phospholipases, lysozyme and amidases, may contribute to bacterial killing (Ellison and Giehl, 1991; Markart et al., 2004; Mollner and Braun, 1984). Normally, heat inactivation of serum is used to inactivate heat-labile complement components, but this method can also inactivate other proteins with an antimicrobial function. This was recently illustrated in a study which found that heat-inactivation blocked serum killing of *E. coli*, but the bactericidal activity of serum was not entirely abolished upon addition of a specific complement inhibitor, indicating that heat inactivation can destroy other bactericidal components in serum (Berends et al., 2015). An approach to block the complement

system by specific inhibitors or using sera in which specific complement factors are depleted is essential to confirm whether killing is complement-dependent. Most studies in *K. pneumoniae* regarding serum resistance focus on changes in the bacterial cell wall, and, more specifically, on modifications of LPS or the capsule. These modifications prevent proper deposition of complement proteins in such a way that no or non-functional MAC is formed (Merino et al., 1992). From a bacterial point of view, inhibition of complement activation at the beginning of the cascade is beneficial, since next to MAC formation, other effector functions such as phagocytosis and neutrophil recruitment are then also blocked (Rooijackers et al., 2005).

Multi-drug resistance of *K. pneumoniae* limits current treatment options to eradicate infections caused by this bacterium. There is an urgent need for novel therapeutic strategies to prevent the increase of life-threatening nosocomial and community-acquired *K. pneumoniae* infections. Several antibiotics are ineffective in Gram-negative bacteria due to their outer membrane barrier. Agents that permeabilize the outer membrane barrier, although lacking antibacterial activity themselves, may sensitize *K. pneumoniae* and other Gram-negative bacteria to antibiotics that are normally ineffective (Vaara et al., 2010). Interestingly, a combination of a polymyxin B derivative (PMBN) and serum has similar synergistic effects (Vaara and Vaara, 1983). Heat-inactivation of serum abolishes the synergy suggesting that PMBN enhances bactericidal activity of the MAC or *vice versa*. The synergy between PMBN and complement is incompletely understood, but probably destabilization of the outer membrane sensitizes complement resistant bacteria to the MAC. For instance, access and deposition of complement components closer to the OM may enhance the proper integration of the MAC into the bacterial OM.

6. Conclusions

K. pneumoniae is ubiquitously present in the environment and has a broad host range. Currently, hypervirulent strains that infect healthy people are emerging, but most of the infections with *K. pneumoniae* are still hospital-acquired and are difficult to treat due to the acquired antibiotic resistance. *K. pneumoniae* has developed mechanisms to adapt during infection to ensure survival within the host, which essentially comprise of improving existing barriers that allow the bacterium to evade complement-dependent killing. The capsule and LPS play an essential role in these complement evasion methods, but are also important in protection against other host defense mechanisms such as antimicrobial peptides. This interplay between complement susceptibility and other bactericidal components provides promising targets for the development of novel therapies against *K. pneumoniae*. Moreover, compared to other opportunistic pathogens *K. pneumoniae* does not secrete host specific complement inhibitors. Therefore, its relatively limited complement resistance mechanisms may also pave the way for more directed immunotherapies to enhance complement-dependent killing of these bacteria.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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